

Title: Numerical solution of weighted multi-state voter model via stochastic differential equations

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INTRODUCTION:

From the mathematical view and probability theory, the **voter model** is a stochastic process that is a specific type of interaction between the data in different groups or particle systems. Voter model has been known as a well-studied Machine Learning predictor model in social opinion dynamics.

AIM:

In this research, we decide to represent an appropriate model and numerical solution for the voter model in the cases in which there are initially some spines, containing states with different ranks. This procedure is a generalized and fairly natural approach of the weighted voter model.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

In the binary or triple case, as the simplest ones, each node in a network is endowed with one of two or three states. In a single update for each step, two nodes are chosen respectively and randomly such that the second one chose a state in its neighborhood. We studied the cases in which there are initially M spines, containing states with different ranks or weights.

We assumed M can take any value from 2 to N , where N are the number of nodes in the network. Each node in the network is initially endowed with one of M possible opinion states denoted by X_1, X_2, \dots, X_M . As the system evolves, it eliminates a state inevitably and completely. That is, there will almost surely be $M - 1$ distinct states in the network at some finite future time. This process is repeated upon consensus time is reached and one opinion dominates the network. According to described method, a system of stochastic differential equations was obtained.

RESULTS:

We applied the first multi-state voter model without weighted spines on the complete graph. In this case, all related stochastic differential equations are without any drift. But, in the second case that is fairly nature, we assumed that spines are categorized in M different groups that each groups also contains subgroups with different strong and week preference. In the fairly case that is more complicated respect to previous one, stochastic differential equations have drift and volatility parts.

CONCLUSIONS:

We applied Euler method as numerical solution of stochastic differential equations and by analyzing the represented weighted multi-state voter model, we reached some appropriate results.

KEYWORDS:

Data Analysis, Machine Learning, Voter Model, Stochastic Differential Equations, Numerical Methods.

BIOGRAPHY:

Hamid is a PhD holder in Applied Math at University of Science and Technology Tehran, Iran (IUST) in 2016. He has an experience of visiting PhD researcher in Computer Science Department at Simon Fraser University (SFU) in 2015-2016. Hamid is a faculty member of Mathematics and statistics department at Karaj Islamic Azad University (KIAU) with more than 20 Journal papers and book publications. Hamid's current research focus is Partial and Stochastic Differential Equations, Data analysis and applied data science based on Numerical Methods and Mathematical Statistics Approach with application in Biology and Financial Markets.